

PHILOSOPHY ON LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT: MEJARITO'S ATHLETIC DIRECTORSHIP THEORY

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ABSTRACT

This study led to the development of a hypothesis on the leadership and management philosophy of an athletic director. The position of athletic director follows a cycle. It is mostly based on one's philosophy, which is influenced by both one's hard (paper and knowledge) and soft (skills) qualities (reputation, values, and gregariousness). In addition, management hard skills (scholastic management), management soft skills (behavioral, financial, and personnel), and leadership hard skills (competencies), leadership soft skills (qualities, values, and orientation), and management hard skills (scholastic management), are essential ingredients to become an efficient and effective Athletic Directors turn to shape-up one's philosophy. An athletic directorship theory was developed as a result of the investigation, based on the growing philosophies of the informants.

Keywords: Athletic Directors, Leadership, Management, Philosophy, Theory Development.

MEJARITO'S ATHLETIC DIRECTORSHIP THEORY

This chapter presents the generated theory based on the gathered data from the informants which result to cross-case analysis as the conclusion of the study. The method used was inductive since it started from the gathering of data from the 12 Athletic Directors of PRISAA (Private Schools Athletic Association) member's schools in Region VII with their narrative accounts about their philosophy on leadership, management and even their qualifications together with the significant events experienced and the problems encountered by the Athletic Directors. Based on the results of the study, the propositions were formulated.

Proposition 1

The philosophy of an Athletic Director on leadership and management is influenced by their exposure to significant events, problems encountered and qualifications of the Athletic Director.

Proposition 2

Significant events are shaped by the philosophy, qualifications and problems encountered by the Athletic Director.

Proposition 3

The qualifications of the Athletic Director are shaped by the philosophy and significant events.

Proposition 4

The problems encountered are shaped by the philosophy and significant events.

The involvement and participation to significant events of the Athletic Director will help develop a more meaningful philosophy. Exposure to the significant events partly is a resultant phenomenon on the decisions and actions when faced with problems. Exposure to the significant events requires that the Athletic Directors to possess the needed qualifications that will allow him to function and perform which will evidently accumulate to the pool of significant events that is useful reference to the future decisions and actions of the Athletic Director. When all are summed, the philosophy of an Athletic Director on leadership and management is strengthened by the cumulative exposure and learning through experience and strengthened with the right qualifications. In trying to understand on what makes a good Athletic Director, we take into account the guiding principles that an Athletic Director believe in. Singly, the philosophies of an Athletic Director mold him to become a well-rounded manager. Thus, when the basic qualifications are intertwined with the philosophies, the result is not just a qualified Athletic Director but an Athletic Director that is guided and well-versed in dealing with the situations that necessitates reference from his experiences.

Tentative Hypotheses

1. The higher you invest in experience the better is your philosophy, the more you invest in your qualification and the better you respond to the problem encountered.
2. The more you are exposed, the higher is the ability to analyze and respond to the situation in reference to the philosophy and learning from the significant events.
3. The synergy of the qualifications, significant events and challenges encountered increases the development of your philosophy.
4. The movement of the philosophy is highly proportional to the direction of the qualifications, significant events and problems encountered.
5. The stronger one's guiding principle is, the better is the one's foundation in directorship.

Though, Athletic Directors have the propensity to be often engaged in significant events the degree reality is that exposure to significant events does not only require a title as "Athletic Director" but more importantly the hard and soft skills of the Athletic Director that adds to the basic qualification. These soft skills include the Athletic Director's reputation, values, and gregariousness alongside his knowledge as hard skill. The soft skills and the hard skills formula enhances the basic qualifications of an Athletic Director. Thereby, contributing a competitive advantage is his participations to the significant events. The rapport of the Athletic Director towards the coaches and student-athletes must be evident in order for them to have a harmonious relationship in dealing with the vision, missions, goals and objectives of the department and the school. An Athletic Director, being a leader, a manager must possess conceptual, relational and technical skills. The basic of all is the third skills technical, which is composed of knowledge and ability, specific to task and job assignment. An Athletic Director therefore should have the necessary information and training on areas relevant to his job, sports and sports programs, wellness, trainings, among them. This competency (technical skills) enables an athletic director to accurately deliver his function and will eventually enhance his qualifications. Basic competencies indeed are the foundation of greater and stronger competencies.

As a common rule, our first impression of the Athletic Director is based on what he writes in his curriculum vitae. These are likely to be his achievements, education, and maybe competencies. But of course, the right person for the job is one that possess more than what the eyes can see his values and reputation. And although it really chance of getting the position that takes time to get to know the values and reputation of an Athletic Director, these two tenets allows heads of organizations to trust better and work well of the Athletic Director and, so, Human Resource personnel should devote time to deeply get to know their Athletic Director inside and out.

Proposition 5

The trust for the hiring of the Athletic Director is highly associated with the hard and soft qualifications.

Proposition 6

Hard qualification comprises all relevant paper qualification and the knowledgeability of the Athletic Director.

Proposition 7

Knowledgeability is the integration of competence with passion, an Athletic Director role as a planner, implementor, decision maker and sports person.

Proposition 8

Soft qualification is the synergy of reputation, values, qualities and gregariousness.

Proposition 9

Reputation is a continuum from personal, familial, sports and management which results to the trust from the administrator.

Proposition 10

Values and qualities involve trustworthiness, honesty, confidence, goal-oriented, values-oriented, values-driven, family-oriented, helpfulness and disciplinarian.

Proposition 11

Gregariousness is the integration of sociability, flexibility, rapport and experiences.

Tentative Hypothesis

6. The higher is the reputation the better is the chance of selection.
7. Possessing favorable values has higher chances of getting the job.
8. The more competence shown the higher the chance of getting the job.
9. The higher the social quotient the higher is the chance of selection.
10. The higher one's competency is the higher the administration's confidence in his capabilities.
11. The more one's possesses good values, the higher is the committee's trust in his discernment.
12. The more outstanding the reputation is the higher the trust of school administration.

Although Athletic Directors usually rise from ranks, they are supposed to possess the needed qualifications for their position, just like everyone else in the organization. These qualifications are so diverse and dynamic that schools really take a lot of considerations before designating an Athletic Director. And since their scope of work involves not only physical functions but also mental, emotional, and social tasks, these qualifications must snugly fit their assignment.

As an Athletic Director, it is important that both hard and soft skill qualifications are present. Just as what the iceberg theory says, what you can see from the outside is only the physical facets of the person. There is more than what meets the eyes. This being considered, an Athletic Director basically should possess the hard qualifications which may include but only limited to his educational background, mastery (knowledgeability) on the subject matter and in his functions, and the skill of course to perform his tasks. These essential requisites are vital foundations in the making of a good Athletic Director.

Other than the hard skill qualifications, more importantly the Athletic Director should also exude a person of unquestionable reputation. This is important so that his subordinates and coordinates would trust and believe in him. Moreover, an Athletic Director has to be gregarious. This trait enables an Athletic Director to exemplify what a true athlete and sportsman is someone with the energy to endure the physico-mental tasks. But the most important of all is to become a reflection of what is good and right. An Athletic Director should be a man of a good values and impeccable qualities. These above all make the Athletic Director not only a man of action but a man of honor as well.

In trying to understand what makes a good Athletic Director, we take into account the guiding principles that an Athletic Director believes in. Singly, the philosophies of an Athletic Director mold him to become a well-rounded manager. Thus, when leadership skills and management skills of an Athletic Director are intertwined to each other towards the philosophy, the result is not just a qualified Athletic Director but an Athletic Director that is guided and well-versed in dealing with situations that necessitate his directing ability.

Proposition 12

Leadership is associated with competency, values, qualities, and orientation. As head of a department, the task of being a leader is one of the major functions and challenges as well as of an Athletic Director. To lead is to influence others to behave and act as the leader desires, and these are the skills not every person can perfect. Leading requires a great deal of trusting relationship beyond knowledge, skills, and attitude. A leader is someone who does not value only for what he can give, but also in what he can do to inspire others to become leaders as well.

But more than the competence aspect, the Athletic Director must also possess the soft facets of a leader. These are his ability to build a trusting relationship to influence others, to interact interpersonally, and to understand socially and emotionally dynamic situations. But of course, these will only be possible if the Athletic Director has a profound understanding and perspective of what being a leader is, coupled by good values and commendable qualities. When all these are put together, the Athletic Director can best lead his group, no matter what it takes.

To become a leader, the Athletic Director needs to have area expertise or should I say, competence. As the saying goes, “you cannot give what you do not have” an Athletic Director can better lead if he possesses the needed competency to perform the tasks well. In this way, he can show to the others that he is capable to deliver what is expected of him. This competence also include decision making skills and as well as conflict management skills.

Tentative Hypotheses

13. The more one’s leadership and management skills are tested the better the philosophy is.
14. The higher the level of competency the better he can associate with people.
15. The higher the values the more he can be a role model.
16. The effectiveness of one’s leadership qualities, affects the efficiency of the Athletic Director.
17. The more oriented is the leader, the swifter he can respond and decide.

Proposition 13

Management skills are associated with scholastic, behavioral, personnel, and financial management.

Through the personal experiences and the significant events emanciated in the Athletic Director's life he could use these as his guiding principles in leadership and evidenced by his leadership style and management application. Management can be viewed as the ability of a person to handle different people and different situations. It goes beyond supervision. Athletic Directors are key personnel who are adept in terms of the methodological functions of management. Just like leading, managing is a skill not anybody can just simply acquire. It develops over time and needs to be nurtured especially when the person is exposed to various situations involving management.

As a manager, the Athletic Director must possess the basic tenets of a leader and these are laid down as a product years of study and education. Management skill is not innate in every person hence; there is a need to root for managerial capacity from the scholastic performance of the Athletic Director. He aims to acquire the right knowledge, skills, and attitude as a basis for an effective management- those that revolve around planning, organizing, directing, and controlling.

But far more than what is learned from school and the development of cognitive intelligence, Athletic Director's management prowess can improve a lot better if he possesses emotional, behavioral, social, and financial intelgence. Emotional and behavioral intelligence allows the Athletic Director to professionally deal with people like his team and subordinates in a manner that promotes trust and confidence. On the other hand, social and financial management skills enables the Athletic Director to manage and be guided with the appropriate principles. These are equally important as with cognitive intelligences. Management is not just about directing people. It is also about ensuring that the organization functions optimally by ascertaining that things are accounted fornately; people, work, resources and output.

Tentative Hypotheses

18. The higher his scholastic, behavioral, financial and personnel management skills the better and Athletic Director is.

Proposition 14

Finding the solutions to the encountered problems are greatly shaped by the management style and leadership skills and his guiding philosophy.

Problems are common in an organization however if an Athletic Director is equipped with the right knowledge, appropriate values, sound leadership styles and effective management skills he could easily make adjustments and find better ways to correct the problems identified . No matter what the nature of the existing problem is, having the qualities stated above, the Athletic Director will be able to successfully arrived at the right solution

Tentative Hypotheses

19. The higher his experience on the problems encountered the better his solution finding-technique.

Mejarito's Athletic Directorship Theory

Athletic Directorship has a cyclical pattern. It is primarily founded on one's philosophy shaped by one's hard qualifications (paper and knowledgeability) and soft qualifications (reputation, values, and gregariousness). In addition to that, the leadership hard skills (competencies), leadership soft skills (qualities, values, and orientation), management hard skills (scholastic management), and management soft skills (behavioral, financial, and personnel) are essential ingredient to become an efficient and effective Athletic Director. Together with the significant events experienced and the problems encountered by the Athletic Directors turn to shape-up one's philosophy. To be appointed and chosen in the position, the hard qualifications and hard skills are the vital factors that can affect the chance of leading and managing people. In order for him to stay in the position, soft qualifications and skills are dynamic nature of an Athletic Director. The relationship of hard skills and soft skills are direct and inseparable. One is meaningless without the other.

To be an efficient and effective Athletic Director, the Mejarito's Athletic Directorship Theory suggests that both hard and soft skills must be evident and applicable. It prompts the School Administration with the cues that warrants the assurance that the potential Athletic Director has a well-rounded personality with a fitting guiding philosophy. It is continuously developed that shape on matured philosophy which ascertain the positive leadership style and management skills that enable the Athletic Director to come up with an effective and efficient decision making and interventions.

Concept of Iceberg Theory

Athletic Directorship has a similar characteristic to an Iceberg Theory that hard skills which are explicit in nature only covers a smaller percentage of the totality of a leader. What may be implicit may not be readily available but is responsible in the sustenance of his directorship. Soft skills are necessary fuel to ignite decisions and actions necessary in the job. Just like an iceberg, the bigger part is down below in which the soft skills covers the bigger percentage in the totality of Athletic Directorship.

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